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1 *External Repository for the Methodology*

2

3 **Study design, setting, and populations**

4 In this retrospective cohort study, we used electronic medical record data of children aged 4–18
5 years with allergies to hen egg or cow milk who underwent an oral food challenge (OFC)^{1–3}
6 twice within 24 months between November 2013 and January 2018 in the Allergy Center of the
7 National Center for Child Health and Development, Tokyo, Japan. Hen egg and cow milk
8 commonly cause of food allergies in Japan⁴; therefore, we selected these allergens for this
9 study. This study was approved by the Ethics Review Committee of the National Center for
10 Child Health and Development (approval number 2027). We published the research plan on the
11 National Center for Child Health and Development homepage and guaranteed an opt-out
12 opportunity in accordance with the ethical approval.

13

14 **Outcome variables for oral immunotherapy (OIT)**

15 We established that the primary outcome of the study was the change in cumulative tolerance
16 dose of the treatment food at the second OFC, adverse events related to OIT during the study
17 observation period, and food-specific immunoglobulin E (IgE) titers. We used fluorescent enzyme
18 immunoassay and ImmunoCAP (Thermo Scientific, Uppsala, Sweden) to measure total serum
19 IgE and egg- or milk-specific IgE levels. The reported range for total serum IgE was 0.1–100
20 kUA/L; levels higher than 0.35 kUA/L were considered positive for allergy.

21

22 **Procedures for oral immunotherapy (OIT)**

23 OIT was performed at home. Figure S1 shows the schema of OIT and avoidance.

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24 We classified the included children into OIT groups according to the four dosing strategies
25 described in Table S1: super ultra-low dose (group A), ultra-low dose (group B), low dose (group
26 C), and conventional slow dose (group D). In addition, children who continued to avoid allergens
27 without OIT were included in the avoidance group (group E). Treatment foods were orally
28 administered based on the OFC threshold for more than three times per week. Children with egg
29 allergy ate hard-boiled egg white (heated 15–20 minutes in boiling water), and those with milk
30 allergy drank nonheated cow milk as OIT. If the children disliked or needed to consume a very
31 small amount of treatment food, they were allowed to consume it along with steamed bread (see
32 Figure S2). The recipe for original steamed bread, which contained rice powder, sugar, baking
33 powder, oil, and treatment food, was developed at our center.⁶ Our nutritionist confirmed the
34 uniform inclusion of the small amount of treatment foods (0.0001 g) in the steamed bread using a
35 food allergen screening test kit (FASTKIT ELISA Ver. III, NH Foods, Tsukubai, Japan) and
36 specific raw materials measurement kit (FASPEC ELIZA II, Morinaga & Company) (Table S6).
37 Physicians determined the starting and maintenance doses. OIT dose was determined based on
38 the OFC result (see Figure S1). All patients regularly visited our center after every 2–3 months,
39 and the allergist checked for the presence of adverse events. During OIT, we also treated patients
40 for other comorbid allergic diseases, such as eczema, asthma, and rhinitis. We intensively treated
41 eczema,⁷ aiming to achieve remission, and performed proactive therapy to prevent flare-ups.

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43 **Statistical analyses**

44 To compare the rates of the groups, we used Fisher's exact test with the false discovery rate to
45 adjust *p* values. To approximate the status of the randomized clinical trial, we performed
46 propensity score weighting analysis to compare the difference in treatment effects between

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47 groups C (who received the low dose) and D (who received the conventional slow dose). The
48 propensity score model was adjusted for age and food-specific IgE level. We obtained relative
49 ratios from a logistic model using the inverse probability of treatment weights. All analyses were
50 performed using R version 4.3.0 software (Institute for Statistics and Mathematics, Vienna,
51 Austria; www.r-project.org; accessed August 1, 2023).

52 **Figure Legends**

53 **FIGURE S1.** Schema of oral immunotherapy (OIT) and avoidance. We classified the children
54 into OIT treatment groups according to four dosing strategies, as described in Table S1: super
55 ultra-low dose (group A), ultra-low dose (group B), low dose (group C), and conventional slow
56 dose (group D). In addition, children who continued to avoid allergens without OIT were
57 included in the avoidance group (group E).

58

59 **FIGURE S2.** The recipe for rice flour steamed bread

60

61 **FIGURE S3.** Flowchart of the study population. Groups A, B, C, D, and E included 33, 51, 17,
62 95, and 21 children, respectively. A total of 217 children met the eligibility criteria until the
63 second oral food challenge (OFC).

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Figure S1. The schema of oral immune therapy

Group A-C: Dosing up regimens

Figure S2-1. Recipe of rice flour steamed bread

Easy Recipe for preparing rice flour steamed bread

Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and Development

Ingredients

Rice Flour	100g
Baking powder	5g
White sugar	25g
Salad oil	5ml
Water	Recipes①—③ 150ml Recipes④ 140ml
Treatment foods (eggs, milk, etc.)	Amounts of Recipes①—④ (see below)

Add 100 g rice flour, 5 g baking powder, and 25 g white sugar in a bowl.

Add 5ml salad oil to the bowl and mix well. (The mixture is parched because of the low moisture content.)

Add 150 ml of water for recipes ①—③ and 140 ml of water for recipe ④.

Next, add the treatment foods (eggs, milk, etc.).

The egg white should be silky and water-soluble.

Recipe ①: 0.1 ml treatment food and 0.9 ml water

Recipe ②: 0.1 ml of treatment food

Recipe ③: 1 ml of treatment food

Recipe ④: 10 ml of treatment food

Add the mixture to the bowl and mix well.

(It is smooth because of the high water content)

Eggs come in two types: smooth aqueous egg whites and elastic thick egg whites. (Ovomucoid content is equivalent.) Aqueous egg whites should preferably be used, as they are easier to mix. It is easier to distinguish the aqueous egg whites and the thick egg whites when served on a flat plate. Since only aqueous egg whites are used, Recipe 4 requires 2 eggs.

Steps for making recipe ①

Take 0.1 ml of treatment food with a syringe (syringe ①)

Serve on a new plate (plate ②)

Take 0.9 ml of water with a syringe (Syringe ②)

Dispense the water into the plate (plate ②)

Mix them both thoroughly using a new syringe by sucking and dispensing the mixture repeatedly (syringe ③)

For recipe ①, take 0.1 ml of therapeutic food and 0.9 ml of water in separate syringes. Mix them well by putting them in and out with a new syringe on a flat plate, and then use 0.1 ml of the mixture.

Figure S2-2. Recipe of rice flour steamed bread

Put the materials which you mixed well in a heat-resistant container. The photo shows a Ziploc plastic container. (It is relatively easy to take out if inserted after oiling the container) Heat the uncovered container in a microwave oven at 500 W for 5 minutes.

When fluffy, it is ready to serve. Remove from the microwave after it has cooled, and it is easy to cut!

When cutting, press the knife vertically on the cutting board to make it easier to cut.

Divide into 48 equal pieces and eat the prescribed amount once a day. The photo shows 48 equal portions divided by making 8 and 6 pieces vertically and horizontally, respectively.

- 1 piece = therapeutic food
- Recipe ① 0.0002 g
- Recipe ② 0.002 g
- Recipe ③ 0.02 g
- Recipe ④ 0.2 g equivalent

It can be frozen and defrosted by heating in a microwave oven at 500 W for 30 seconds.

If left at room temperature for a long time, it will dry out and denature; therefore, if you do not plan on eating it immediately, it is recommended to freeze it.

Rice-flour steamed bread with egg white or milk intake

	Recipe①	Recipe②	Recipe③	Recipe④
Use Ingredients	0.01 ml of treatment food (mix 0.1ml of treatment food with 0.9ml of water and use 0.1ml from it)	0.1 ml of treatment food	1 ml of treatment food	10 ml of treatment food
Cutting method	48 equal parts (cut into 8 x 6 pieces)			
Content per piece	48 equal parts = 0.0002 g/piece	48 equal parts = 0.002 g/piece	48 equal parts = 0.02 g/piece	48 equal parts = 0.2 g/piece
Amount of allergen actually eaten daily (g)	0.0001	0.5 pieces		
	0.0002	1 piece		
	0.0004	2 pieces		
	0.0008	4 pieces		
	0.0016	8 pieces	0.5 pieces (3/4 pieces)	
	0.0032		1.5 pieces	
	0.0064		3 pieces	
	0.013		6 pieces	0.5 pieces
	0.026			1 piece
0.051			2.5 pieces	
0.1			5 pieces	0.5 pieces
0.2				1 piece
0.4				2 pieces
0.8				4 pieces

The sweetness and moisture content can be adjusted. You can eat it as it is or dip it in jam or honey. Be creative and eat it deliciously without getting bored!

The amount of antigens from the above recipe is constant and evenly mixed has been measured and confirmed by a doctor from the University of Nutrition and Dietetics.

Figure S3. Flowchart of the participants

Table S1. Oral Immunotherapy Types

OIT Types	Starting Dose	Maintenance Dose
Super ultra-low dose (group A)	1/10,000 of the first OFC threshold The dose (1/10,000 of the first OFC threshold) was doubled in the second week, and each dose was doubled after every 1–2 weeks.	1/10 of the first OFC dose until the end of OIT Under threshold
Ultra-low dose (group B)	1/100 of the first OFC threshold The dose (1/10 of the first OFC threshold) was increased by 10% of the initial dose every 1–2 weeks.	1/10 of the first OFC threshold Under threshold
Low dose (group C)	1/10 of the first OFC threshold	1/10 of the first OFC threshold is maintained until the end of OIT Under threshold

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Conventional slow dose (group D)	Full OFC threshold The dose was increased 1.2–1.5 times every few weeks	Increased to more than the threshold dose (this method is currently conventionally used in Japan)
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OFC, oral food challenge; OIT, oral immunotherapy.

Table S2. Characteristics of Study Population

	All Children	Group A Super ultra-low dose	Group B Ultra-low dose	Group C Low-dose	Group D Conventional slow dose	Group E Avoidance
Patients, n	217	33	51	17	95	21
Age (years), median (IQR)	6.0 (5.0–8.0)	7.0 (5.0–9.0)	5.0 (4.0–6.5)	6.0 (4.0–10.0)	6.0 (5.0–8.5)	5.0 (5.0–7.0)
Males, n (%)	142 (65.4%)	20 (60.6%)	34 (68.6%)	13 (76.5%)	61 (64.2%)	14 (66.7%)
History of atopic dermatitis, n (%)	148 (68.2%)	26 (78.8%)	33 (64.7%)	12 (70.6%)	65 (68.4%)	12 (57.1%)
History of asthma, n (%)	86 (39.6%)	16 (48.5%)	14 (27.5%)	11 (64.7%)	37 (38.9%)	8 (38.1%)
Duration of oral immunotherapy (months), median (IQR)	16 (12–22)	14(11–17)	15 (12–18)	18 (14–24)	17 (12–22)	22 (12–24)

Data are expressed as n (%), median (IQR), or n/N (%).

Percentages indicate the number of patients in each category/total patients in each group.

IQR, interquartile range

Table S3 Comparison between the OIT in the low-dose (groups A–C) and conventional slow dose (group D) groups

	RR	95%CI		<i>P</i>
		Lower	Upper	
1) Increase in the cumulative tolerated dose of the allergen				
Egg_GroupABC vs. Group D	1.324	0.974	1.801	0.073
Milk_GroupABC vs. Group D	1.488	1.129	1.961	0.005
2) Adverse event during oral immunotherapy				
Egg_GroupABC vs. Group D	0.215	0.102	0.453	<0.001
Milk_GroupABC vs. Group D	0.379	0.23	0.623	<0.001
3) Decrease in food-specific IgE				
EggGroupABC vs. Group D	0.974	0.852	1.114	0.702
Milk_GroupABC vs. Group D	1.163	0.954	1.419	0.136

RR: relative risk; CI: confidence interval.

Owing to the small sample size, we combined groups A, B, and C into one group and removed the group E; the treatment effects were compared between the low-dose group (A–C) and conventional dose group (D).

To counteract the drawbacks of the observational study design, we performed a propensity score (PS) weighting analysis to evaluate the treatment effect. Age and specific IgE before OIT were adjusted in the PS model.

RR was calculated via Inverse probability of treatment weights (IPW),

Table S4. Oral food challenge test data and laboratory data of the patients.

	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	
All Children	Super ultra-low dose	Ultra-low dose	Low dose	Conventional slow dose	Avoidance	
No. of egg allergy patients, n	103	19	30	6	37	11
Oral food challenge test Data of Egg allergy patients						
Cumulative tolerated dose of egg white protein before OIT, (mg), median (IQR)	708.8 (200.3–1102.5)	367.5 (26.2–787.5)	399.0 (122.1–874.1)	448.9 (74.8–1575.0)	1050.0 (695.6–1848.0)	787.5 (299.2–787.5)
Cumulative tolerated dose of egg white protein after OIT, (mg), median (IQR)	1050.0 (359.6–3150.0)	631.0 (325.0–791.0)	1050.0 (246.8–2730.0)	393.8 (328.1–931.9)	1942.5 (903.0–3806.2)	262.5 (70.9–892.5)
Laboratory data of egg allergy patients						
Total IgE before OIT, (U _A /ml), median (IQR)	628.0 (281.8–1357.5)	631.0 (325.0–791.0)	535.0 (302.3–1171.5)	750.5 (539.8–2138.0)	945.0 (202.8–2394.8)	557.0 (265.0–860.0)
Total IgE after OIT, (U _A /ml), median (IQR)	638.0 (311.0–1225.0)	387.0 (253.0–789.0)	624.0 (346.0–1075.0)	1090.0 (814.8–4480.0)	763.5 (296.8–1875.0)	902.0 (466.0–1115.0)
Egg white-specific IgE before OIT, (IU/ml), median (IQR)	29.4 (11.8–64.3)	34.4 (8.8–98.1)	44.7 (19.1–100.0)	35.7 (24.7–51.2)	20.4 (8.8–52.6)	19.8 (8.5–35.9)
Egg white-specific IgE after OIT, (IU/ml), median (IQR)	16.6 (6.4–42.5)	18.6 (3.7–57.8)	27.3 (10.7–60.0)	26.2 (19.7–82.3)	16.1 (5.1–30.9)	7.5 (5.7–23.2)

No. of milk allergy patients, n	114	14	21	11	58	10
Oral food challenge test Data of Milk allergy patients						
Cumulative tolerated dose of milk protein before OIT, (mg), median (IQR)	283.8 (34.6-1155)	132 (34.6-577.5)	34.6 (33-105.6)	89.1 (26.4-207.9)	569.2 (283.8-2227.5)	156.8 (20.6-1072.5)
Cumulative tolerated dose of milk protein after OIT, (mg), median (IQR)	445.5 (82.5-2722.5)	132 (34.6-1254)	132 (115.5-330)	52.8 (33.8-183.2)	1980 (470.2-4950)	74.2 (34.6-280.5)
Laboratory data of milk allergy patients						
Total IgE before OIT, (U _A /ml), median (IQR)	648.0 (279.5–1418.8)	1050.0 (385.0–1800.0)	541.0 (153.0–1480.0)	357.0 (258.0–893.0)	653.0 (362.0–1300.0)	1092.5 (289.5–1450.2)
Total IgE after OIT, (U _A /ml), median (IQR)	656.0 (336.0–1540.0)	824.5 (457.3–1600.0)	700.0 (288.5–1220.0)	593.0 (300.5–795.0)	656.0 (364.0–1600.0)	789.5 (223.5–1495.0)
Milk-specific IgE before OIT, (IU/ml), median (IQR)	18.1 (4.5–49.9)	42.5 (19.3–70.0)	27.8 (4.4–57.7)	35.1 (25.2–96.1)	8.5 (3.1–30.6)	20.2 (7.8–60.7)
Milk-specific IgE after OIT, (IU/ml), median (IQR)	11.4 (3.1–37.2)	33.3 (12.8–61.3)	18.8 (5.4–50.5)	45.8 (13.2–87.6)	4.8 (1.3–18.8)	18.1 (7.0–51.0)

Data are expressed as n (%), median (IQR), or n/N (%).

Percentages indicate the number of patients in each category/total patients in each group.

IgE, immunoglobulin E; IQR, Interquartile Range; OFC, oral food challenge; OIT, oral immunotherapy

Table S5. Events for Each Group During Oral Immunotherapy

	All Children	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D
		Super ultra-low dose	Ultra-low dose	Low-dose	Conventional slow dose
Patients, n	217	33	51	17	95
Patients with adverse events, n (%)	87 (40.1%)	8 (24.2%)	7 (13.7%)	5 (29.4%)	67 (70.5%)
Itchy mouth/throat	49 (22.6%)	6 (18.2%)	5 (9.8%)	4 (2.4%)	34 (35.8%)
Rash, n (%)	15 (6.9%)	1 (3.0%)	-	-	14 (14.7%)
Urticaria, n (%)	11 (5.1%)	-	-	-	11 (11.6%)
Frequent dry cough, n (%)	7 (3.2%)	-	-	-	7 (7.4%)
Abdominal pain, n (%)	9 (4.1%)	1 (3.0%)	1 (2.0)	1 (5.9%)	6 (6.3%)
Wheezing, n (%)	4 (1.8%)	-	-	-	4 (4.2%)
Lip or face edema, n (%)	4 (1.8%)	-	-	-	4 (4.2%)
Emesis, n (%)	4 (1.8%)	-	1 (2.0)	-	4 (4.2%)
Diarrhea, n (%)	2 (0.9%)	-	-	-	2 (2.1%)
Nausea, n (%)	1 (0.5%)	-	-	-	1 (1.1%)
Hoarseness, n (%)	1 (0.5%)	-	-	-	1 (1.1%)
Anaphylaxis, n (%)	14 (6.5%)	-	-	-	14 (14.7%)

Percentages indicate the number of patients in each category/total patients in each group.

Table S6 The egg antigen levels in various states of eggs and steamed bread

Sample number	Measuring kit	FASTKIT ELISA Ver. III	FASPEK ELIZA II
		Egg protein content (including Ovomuroid) in 1 g steamed bread (mg/g)	Ovalbumin in 1 g steamed bread (mg/g)
1	Raw egg white	128	71.8
2	Raw egg yolk	3.23	0.909
3	Egg white peeled immediately after boiling (egg was started to boil in boiling water and heated for 15 minutes)	90.5	35.6
4	Egg yolk peeled immediately after boiling (egg was started to boil in boiling water and heated for 15 minutes)	3.24	1.22
5	Egg yolk peeled after one hour of boiling (egg was started to boil in boiling water and heated for 15 minutes)	3.77	1.26
6	Frozen egg white, peeled immediately after boiling (egg was started to boil in room temperature water and heated for 15 minutes after boiling)	82.9	37.3
7	Room temperature egg white, peeled immediately after boiling (egg was started to boil in room temperature water and heated for 15 minutes after boiling).	66.8	28.7
8	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Top	0.00575	0.00309
9	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Bottom	0.00448	0.00393
10	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Edge	0.00433	0.00484
11	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Edge, Room temperature	0.00275	0.00246
12	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Frozen	0.00588	0.00446
13	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Frozen, and microwave heating	0.00649	0.00618
14	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Room temperature	0.00336	0.00351
15	Recipe ① Egg white 0.01 mL Room temperature, and microwave heating	0.00435	0.00375
16	Recipe ② Egg white 0.1 mL Top	0.0405	0.0238
17	Recipe ② Egg white 0.1 mL Bottom	0.0365	0.0278

18	Recipe ② Egg white 0.1 mL Edge	0.0414	0.0232
19	Recipe ③ Egg white 1 mL Top	0.333	0.248
20	Recipe ③ Egg white 1 mL Bottom	0.471	0.260
21	Recipe ③ Egg white 1 mL Edge	0.358	0.279
22	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Top	4.09	3.41
23	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Bottom	4.70	2.32
24	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Edge	3.94	2.35
25	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Room temperature	3.15	1.77
26	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Frozen	5.08	3.64
27	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL frozen, and microwave heating	4.86	3.75
28	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Room temperature	2.73	2.39
29	Recipe ④ Egg white 10 mL Room temperature, microwave heating	2.87	2.11

“TOP” is the top layer of the finished steamed bread

“Bottom” is the bottom layer of the finished steamed bread

“Edge” is the edge of the finished steamed bread

“Frozen” is the finished steamed bread frozen in a household refrigerator.

“Microwave heating” is the heating of the steamed bread in a 500W microwave oven for 30 seconds.

“Room temperature” is the finished steamed bread kept at room temperature.